

21NRM05 STASIS

D6: Report on the determination of the uncertainty budget for smart implants, the RF exposure system and gradient induced heating

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Glossary

AIMD - Active Implantable *Medical* Device

RF - Radiofrequency

SAR – Specific Absorption Rate

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SUMMARY

Determination of the uncertainty in any measurement that is related to the MRI device performance is a complicated task that is affected by

- a) a complexity of the measurement problem,
- b) complicated definition of the output quantity,
- c) problems with the definition of the functional dependence among input quantities and the output quantity,
- d) determination of the influence quantities,
- e) quantification of the input quantities and influence quantities.

Among others, the heating of the implant due to the electric and magnetic field generated during the MRI device operation is widely investigated to enable safe use of an MRI device also for patients with implants. Within project STASIS several research activities are conducted by different research groups on the topic referring to radiofrequency (RF) induced implant heating and gradient induced implant heating.

This document focusses on the uncertainty budget calculations of gradient induced implant heating as mainly investigated by INRIM (Italy), while ČMI and STU Bratislava provide their support in statistical analysis of the obtained data. Therefore this document aims at the two tasks, being carried out by ČMI and STU Bratislava, that were asked for and defined by INRIM. Those two task are

- a) finding the correlation between the power deposited into the implant under different conditions and the following temperature increase, together with the associated uncertainty,
- b) Performing the statistical analysis of the deviations between the experimental and numerical results, while accounting for the relevant uncertainties.

The details about both tasks are provided directly in the respective chapter. The analysis of the results and their physical interpretation are carried out by INRIM. Therefore, those analyses and interpretations should be sought in the deliverable *D4 Report on the technical specifications and guidelines for comprehensive testing of gradient-induced heating of passive implants*.

RF induced implant heating and the corresponding uncertainty calculations are found in the following documents:

- Deliverable D1: Report on the development and calibration of an implant safety concept in MRI, comprised of sensor-equipped smart medical implants and pTx capable MRI scanners that enable to assess and mitigate in situ RF induced implant heating. Lead participant: PTB (Germany).
- Deliverable D3: Report on the development of open-source reference hardware (RF coil, exciter, modulators, RF power amplifiers) and open-source control software, including traceable measurement procedures that allow testing of implant under parallel transmission (pTx) MR conditions. Lead participant: DKFZ (Germany).
- Deliverable D5: Report on the translation of in vitro safety testing results to realistic exposure conditions considering combined GC and RF induced heating. Lead participant: IT'IS (Switzerland).

In summary, the aims of the STASIS project deliverable have been successfully achieved, fulfilling Objective 1-3 of the project.

Task A: Finding the correlation between the power deposited into the implant and the following temperature increase

Scope

Determination of the relationship between the induced power and the temperature increase of the implant due to gradient induced implant heating in MRI. Four implants are considered in this document:

- a. Hip
- b. Knee
- c. Shoulder
- d. Ankle Plate

THE STANDARDIZATION BACKGROUND

Technical specification ISO/TS 10974

Technical specification ISO/TS 10974 *Assessment of the safety of magnetic resonance imaging for patients with an active implantable medical device* contains two chapters that deal with harm to the patient by the MRI generated heat:

- Chapter 8 Protection from harm to the patient caused by RF-induced heating
- Chapter 9 Protection from harm to the patient caused by gradient-induced device heating

In the *chapter 8*, the point 8.4.4.4 states that the local temperature rise ΔT or SAR at a point location in a hot spot produced by the AIMD can be related to the total power deposition using a calibrated RF power injection method. For each AIMD hot spot, a conversion factor m between ΔT or SAR at the hot spot and injected power is experimentally determined (i.e. $\Delta T = m \cdot P_{\text{inject}}$ or $\text{SAR} = m \cdot P_{\text{inject}}$).

In *chapter 9*, the standard states that the imaging gradient field dB/dt induces eddy currents on conductive AIMD enclosures and other conductive internal surfaces that result in device heating. The heating will be greatest for implants with a large surface area and high electrical conductivity. Typically, the heating is greatest when the device is oriented so that the gradient field vector is orthogonal to the AIMD surface(s) with the largest conductive area. Device heating could also depend on the gradient waveform characteristics.

Technical report ISO/TR 21900

Technical report ISO/TR 21900 *Guidance for uncertainty analysis regarding the application of ISO/TS 10974* in its part 4 introduces two methods for uncertainty evaluation (in practice, overlaps between those methods exist):

- a) Method 1 (part 4.2 of the TR) determines the uncertainty of the measurement system by considering the variability of the system as a whole. In this method, multiple elements of the system are assembled together, and their combined uncertainty is assessed. This is the method that we employed for evaluating the preliminary results, as presented in this report.
- b) Method 2 (part 4.3 of the TR) dissects the assembly into its parts, determines the uncertainty of individual elements, and then determines the uncertainty of the group by combining the uncertainty of the components.

1. DEFINITION OF THE TASK

Input data

Each implant is associated with an activity1_mat file containing the following variables:

- **power_map** : $N_\theta \times N_\phi$ matrix of the total power expressed in watts deposited into the implant for a specific orientation of the unitary harmonic magnetic field expressed in polar coordinates. θ : $[0, \pi/2]$ is the polar angle (the angle between the magnetic field vector and the z -axis), and ϕ : $[-\pi, \pi]$ is the azimuth angle (the angle between the magnetic field vector and the 1 x -axis). N_θ and N_ϕ are the numbers of θ and ϕ intervals at which the power has been computed;
- **power_worst_H** : 3-element vector representing the unitary magnetic field that results in the maximum power deposited into the implant;
- **temp_map_min** : $N_\theta \times N_\phi$ matrix of the maximum temperature increase expressed in kelvin, after minutes of exposure, for a specific orientation of the unitary harmonic magnetic field expressed in polar coordinates with the same criteria used in the power_map matrix;
- **temp_worst_H_min** : 3-element vector representing the unitary magnetic field that results in the maximum temperature increase after minutes of exposure;
- **external_surface** : external surface of the implant expressed in square meters (i.e., the interface between the implant and the background).

Each of the particular data files power_map, temp_map_min contains 40,000 data points (for any theta and phi combination it is one data point). The three files temp_map_min were received, for 5 minutes, 15 minutes, and 30 minutes.

The task

It is expected that the following points are investigated in the framework of the activity:

1. For each implant, the correlation between the magnetic field direction that maximises the power deposition into the implant and that maximises the temperature increase after 5 minutes, 15 minutes, and 30 minutes of exposure;
2. For each implant, the correlation between the power deposited into the implant and the following temperature increase as a function of the magnetic field direction. The correlation should be evaluated by accounting for a temperature increase after 5 minutes, 15 minutes, and 30 minutes of exposure;
3. For each implant, a coefficient, with associated uncertainty/confidence level, that allows estimating the temperature increase after a specified time instant given the power deposited into the implant.

2. SOLUTION

The following text of this document deals with point 3 of the formulated task, i.e. finding the dependence between the deposited power and a temperature rise, including the respective uncertainty.

2.1 Definition of the solved task

Therefore, the task is determining the relationship between the deposited power (denoted as X), and the temperature difference after a given time of 5, 15, and 30 minutes (denoted as Y). It is assumed that this relationship can be approximated by linear regression, i.e. a theoretical model is

$$Y = \beta X$$

or

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X$$

The task is to determine:

1. for $Y = \beta X$
 - a. estimate b the unknown coefficient β of the line,
 - b. the uncertainty u_b ;
2. for $Y = \alpha + \beta X$
 - a. estimates a and b the unknown coefficients α and β of the line,
 - b. their uncertainties u_a , u_b , and covariance among them u_{ab} .

If we determine those parameters, for any given x (the value of power) we can calculate the value of y (the temperature difference) and its corresponding uncertainty u_y .

Moreover, an additional calculation was carried out, where the deposited power was transferred to energy, and the relation between energy and the temperature increase was investigated.

2.2 Theoretical background

The two forms of linear regression will be investigated:

- a. the linear regression (line) which crosses the zero point (intersection of x and y axes),
- b. the linear regression (line) which is shifted from the zero point (intersection of x and y axes)

2.2.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Employing the least squares method, the unknown coefficient b can be determined as follows:

$$b = \frac{1}{\sum x_i^2} \sum x_i y_i$$

where

x_i is the measured power input value (from the supplied data),

y_i is the measured temperature rise (from the supplied data).

2. The uncertainty u_b of the coefficient b can be determined as follows:

$$u_b = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum x_i^2}} s,$$

where s can be estimated by a formula for sample residual variance

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i - (bx_i)]^2}$$

3. The uncertainty u_y of the calculated value $y = bx$ can be determined as follows:

$$u_y = x u_b = x \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum x_i^2}} s$$

4. Coefficient of determination R^2 is a statistical measure of how well the regression predictions approximate the real data points

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - bx_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

5. Confidence intervals (UCL, LCL)

$$y \pm t_{n-1, 1-\alpha/2} u_y$$

$$y \pm t_{n-1, 1-\alpha/2} s \sqrt{\frac{x}{\sum x_i^2}}$$

6. Prediction intervals (UPL, LPL)

$$y \pm t_{n-1, 1-\alpha/2} s \sqrt{1 + \frac{x}{\sum x_i^2}}$$

7. Tolerance intervals (UTL, LTL)

$$y \pm k_{2, 1-\alpha/2, p, n} s$$

8. Uncertainty of conversion is determined as follows. The expanded uncertainty $U_{y, \text{conv}}$ of the temperature increase ΔT obtained by conversion from deposited power is defined as half the interval between the upper and lower tolerance limits (UTL resp. LTL), the interval that represents $(1-\alpha) \cdot 100 = 95\%$ certainty that there is a $p \cdot 100 = 90\%$ chance, that the correct prediction of ΔT lies between the upper and lower limits of the tolerance interval, i.e.

$$U_{y, \text{conv}} = k_{2, 1-\alpha/2, p, n} s$$

where

$$k_{2, 1-\alpha/2, p, n} = k_{2, 0,975, 0,9, n}$$

2.2.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Employing the least squares method, the unknown coefficients a , and b can be determined as follows:

$$a = \frac{\sum x_i^2 \sum y_i - \sum x_i \sum x_i y_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2}$$

$$b = \frac{n \sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2}$$

2. The uncertainties u_a , u_b of both coefficients a , and b can be determined as follows:

$$u_a^2 = \frac{\sum x_i^2}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} s^2$$

$$u_b^2 = \frac{n}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} s^2$$

where

$$s^2 = \frac{1}{n-2} \sum (y_i - \hat{y})^2 = \frac{1}{n-2} \sum (y_i - a - bx_i)^2$$

3. The covariance $u_{a,b}$ between the two coefficients a , and b can be determined as follows:

$$u_{a,b} = \frac{-\sum x_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} s^2$$

4. The uncertainty u_y of the calculated value y can be determined as follows (the formula for u_y^2 is stated here):

$$u_y^2 = u_a^2 + x^2 \cdot u_b^2 + 2 \cdot x \cdot u_{a,b}$$

5. Coefficient of determination R^2 is a statistical measure of how well the regression predictions approximate the real data points

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - a - bx_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

6. Confidence intervals (UCL, LCL)

$$y \pm t_{n-1, 1-\alpha/2} u_y$$

$$y \pm t_{n-1, 1-\alpha/2} s \sqrt{\frac{1}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} (\sum x_i^2 + n x^2 - 2 x \sum x_i)}$$

7. Prediction intervals (UPL, LPL)

$$y \pm t_{n-1, 1-\alpha/2} s \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} (\sum x_i^2 + n x^2 - 2 x \sum x_i)}$$

8. Tolerance intervals (UTL, LTL)

$$y \pm k_{2, 1-\alpha/2, p, n} s$$

9. Uncertainty of conversion is determined as follows. The expanded uncertainty $U_{y,\text{conv}}$ of the temperature increase ΔT obtained by conversion from deposited power is defined as half the interval between the upper and lower tolerance limits (UTL resp. LTL), the interval that represents $(1-\alpha)\cdot 100 = 95\%$ certainty that there is a $p\cdot 100 = 90\%$ chance, that the correct prediction of ΔT lies between the upper and lower limits of the tolerance interval, i.e.

$$U_{y,\text{conv}} = k_{2,1-\alpha/2,p,n} s$$

where

$$k_{2,1-\alpha/2,p,n} = k_{2,0,975,0,9,n}$$

3. Transferring the deposited power into energy

$$x/W = \frac{x/\text{J}}{t/\text{s}}$$

where

J is joule

W is watt

t is the respective time (5, 15, 30 minutes, converted to seconds)

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

Based on theory stated in chapter 2, the following text contain calculated values for all four implants and for the two forms of the linear regression.

3.1 Ankle Plate

3.1.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{ankpla5m}_b} =$	1,4712125 K/W	$u_{\text{bankpla5m}_b} =$	0,001575301 K/W
$R_{\text{ankpla5m}_b}^2 =$	0,87048183	$S_{\text{ankpla5m}_b} =$	$2,21147 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convankpla5m}_b} =$	$3,63764 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{ankpla15m}_b} =$	2,115517798 K/W	$u_{\text{bankpla15m}_b} =$	0,002179237 K/W
$R_{\text{ankpla15m}_b}^2 =$	0,881844433	$S_{\text{ankpla15m}_b} =$	$3,05929 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convankpla15m}_b} =$	$5,03223 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

3. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{ankpla30m}_b} =$	2,552769599 K/W	$u_{\text{bankpla30m}_b} =$	0,002517638 K/W
$R_{\text{ankpla30m}_b}^2 =$	0,892606045	$S_{\text{ankpla30m}_b} =$	$3,53435 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convankpla30m}_b} =$	$5,81366 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

4. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{ankpla_energy}_b} =$	0.00167640 K/J	$u_{\text{bankpla_energy}_b} =$	$1.75226396 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K/J
$R_{\text{ankpla_energy}_b}^2 =$	0.70249781	$S_{\text{ankpla_energy}_b} =$	$5.00514001 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convankpla_energy}_b} =$	$8.23295 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

Remark: Please note that the correlation coefficient indicates a weak linear relationship, compared to the dependence of temperature increase on the deposited power after 5, 15, and 30 minutes. Please compare with the correlation coefficient for $Y = \beta X$.

3.1.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$\alpha_{\text{ankpla5m}_{ab}} =$	$2.29836 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K	$u_{\alpha_{\text{ankpla5m}_{ab}}} =$	$1.39716 \cdot 10^{-13}$ K
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$b_{\text{ankpla5m_ab}} =$	1.230235528 K/W	$u_{\text{bankpla5m_ab}} =$	0.001990482 K/W
		$u_{a,\text{bankpla5m_ab}} =$	$-2.04667 \cdot 10^{-16}$ K ² /W
$R_{\text{ankpla5m_ab}}^2 =$	0.90521686	$S_{\text{ankpla5m_ab}} =$	$1.89187 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convankpla5m_ab}} =$	$3,11193 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{ankpla15m_ab}} =$	$3.111633 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K	$u_{a\text{ankpla15m_ab}} =$	$1.94668 \cdot 10^{-13}$ K
$b_{\text{ankpla15m_ab}} =$	1.788778401 K/W	$u_{\text{bankpla15m_ab}} =$	0.002773366 K/W
		$u_{a,\text{bankpla15m_ab}} =$	$-3.97324 \cdot 10^{-16}$ K ² /W
$R_{\text{ankpla15m_ab}}^2 =$	0.912285715	$S_{\text{ankpla15m_ab}} =$	$2.63597 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convankpla15m_ab}} =$	$4,3359 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

3. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{ankpla30m_ab}} =$	$3.58566 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K	$u_{a\text{ankpla30m_ab}} =$	$2.25212 \cdot 10^{-13}$ K
$b_{\text{ankpla30m_ab}} =$	2.17682236 K/W	$u_{\text{bankpla30m_ab}} =$	0.003208518 K/W
		$u_{a,\text{bankpla30m_ab}} =$	$-5.3179 \cdot 10^{-16}$ K ² /W
$R_{\text{ankpla30m_ab}}^2 =$	0.920050979	$S_{\text{ankpla30m_ab}} =$	$3.04956 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convankpla30m_ab}} =$	$5,01622 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

4. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{ankpla_energy_ab}} =$	$5.41049901 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K	$u_{a\text{ankpla_energy_ab}} =$	$1.57443568 \cdot 10^{-13}$ K
$b_{\text{ankpla_energy_ab}} =$	0.00126533 K/J	$u_{\text{bankpla_energy_ab}} =$	$1.90940847 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K/J
		$u_{a,\text{bankpla_energy_ab}} =$	$-1,88333940 \cdot 10^{-19}$ K ² /J
$R_{\text{ankpla_energy_ab}}^2 =$	0.78539134	$S_{\text{ankpla_energy_ab}} =$	$4,25107123 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convankpla_energy_ab}} =$	$6,99259 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

3.2 Hip

3.2.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{hip5m_b}} =$	1.133156432 K/W	$u_{b\text{hip5m_b}} =$	0,000464882 K/W
$R_{\text{hip5m_b}}^2 =$	0.774842384	$S_{\text{hip5m_b}} =$	$2.6571 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convhip5m_b}} =$	$0.874 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{hip15m}_b} =$	1.897958636 K/W	$u_{b\text{hip15m}_b} =$	0,000605093 K/W
$R_{\text{hip15m}_b^2} =$	0.782750617	$S_{\text{hip15m}_b} =$	$3.4585 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convhip15m}_b} =$	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

3. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{hip30m}_b} =$	2.49762561 K/W	$u_{b\text{hip30m}_b} =$	0.000734206 K/W
$R_{\text{hip30m}_b^2} =$	0.816735899	$S_{\text{hip30m}_b} =$	$4.19646 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convhip30m}_b} =$	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

4. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{hip_energy}_b} =$	0.001580637 K/J	$u_{b\text{hip_energy}_b} =$	$1.11056 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K/J
$R_{\text{hip_energy}_b^2} =$	0.467604763	$S_{\text{hip_energy}_b} =$	$1.29154 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,645$	$U_{y,\text{convhip_energy}_b} =$	$2.12 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

Remark: Please note that the correlation coefficient indicates a weak linear relationship, compared to the dependence of temperature increase on the deposited power after 5, 15, and 30 minutes. Please compare with the correlation coefficient for $Y = \beta X$.

3.2.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{hip5m}_{ab}} =$	$1.20576 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K	$u_{a\text{hip5m}_{ab}} =$	$8.38027 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{\text{hip5m}_{ab}} =$	1.09149561 K/W	$u_{b\text{hip5m}_{ab}} =$	0.002932398 K/W
		$u_{a,b\text{hip5m}_{ab}} =$	$-2.42651 \cdot 10^{-14}$ K ² /W
$R_{\text{hip5m}_{ab}^2} =$	0.775978489	$S_{\text{hip5m}_{ab}} =$	$2.65045 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convhip5m}_{ab}} =$	$0,872 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{hip15m}_{ab}} =$	$1.13769 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K	$u_{a\text{hip15m}_{ab}} =$	$9.38244 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{\text{hip15m}_{ab}} =$	1.504872446 K/W	$u_{b\text{hip15m}_{ab}} =$	0.003283074 K/W
		$u_{a,b\text{hip15m}_{ab}} =$	$-3.04156 \cdot 10^{-14}$ K ² /W
$R_{\text{hip15m}_{ab}^2} =$	0.840074435	$S_{\text{hip15m}_{ab}} =$	$2.96741 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convhip15m}_{ab}} =$	$0,976 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

3. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{hip30m_ab}} =$	$1.3879 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$	$u_{a\text{hip30m_ab}} =$	$1.13623 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{hip30m_ab}} =$	2.018085947 K/W	$u_{b\text{hip30m_ab}} =$	0.003975858 K/W
		$u_{a,b\text{hip30m_ab}} =$	$-4.46064 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{hip30m_ab}}^2 =$	0.865616434	$S_{\text{hip30m_ab}} =$	$3.59359 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convhip30m_ab}} =$	$0,59 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$

4. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{hip_energy_ab}} =$	$2.59697 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$	$u_{a\text{hip_energy_ab}} =$	$2.76696 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{hip_energy_ab}} =$	0.000930428 K/J	$u_{b\text{hip_energy_ab}} =$	$8.24191 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ K/J}$
		$u_{a,b\text{hip_energy_ab}} =$	$-1.91687 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ K}^2/\text{J}$
$R_{\text{hip_energy_ab}}^2 =$	0.913943425	$S_{\text{hip_energy_ab}} =$	$5.1926 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,645$	$U_{y,\text{convhip_energy_ab}} =$	$0,85 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ K}$

3.3 Knee

3.3.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{knee5m_b}} =$	$1,145453 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{b\text{knee5m_b}} =$	$0,000474923 \text{ K/W}$
$R_{\text{knee5m_b}}^2 =$	$0,95915549$	$S_{\text{knee5m_b}} =$	$2,95055 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convknee5m_b}} =$	$4,85336 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{knee15m_b}} =$	$1,777887961 \text{ K/W}$	$u_{b\text{knee15m_b}} =$	$0,00063443 \text{ K/W}$
$R_{\text{knee15m_b}}^2 =$	$0,97002198$	$S_{\text{knee15m_b}} =$	$3,94152 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convknee15m_b}} =$	$6,4834 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$

3. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{knee30m_b}} =$	2.278559419 K/W	$u_{b\text{knee30m_b}} =$	0.000708149 K/W
$R_{\text{knee30m_b}}^2 =$	0.977212809	$S_{\text{knee30m_b}} =$	$4.39951 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convknee30m_b}} =$	$7,23676 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$

4. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{knee_energy_b}} =$	0.00146018 K/J	$u_{b\text{knee_energy_b}} =$	$1.18299463 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K/J
$R_{\text{knee_energy_b}}^2 =$	0.68011614	$S_{\text{knee_energy_b}} =$	$1,49541816 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convknee_energy_b}} =$	$2,45981 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

Remark: Please note that the correlation coefficient indicates a weak linear relationship, compared to the dependence of temperature increase on the deposited power after 5, 15, and 30 minutes. Please compare with the correlation coefficient for $Y = \beta X$.

3.3.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{knee5m_ab}} =$	$3.3659 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K	$u_{a\text{knee5m_ab}} =$	$3.6362 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{\text{knee5m_ab}} =$	1.135547694 K/W	$u_{b\text{knee5m_ab}} =$	0.001170572 K/W
		$u_{a,b\text{knee5m_ab}} =$	$-3.89104 \cdot 10^{-15}$ K ² /W
$R_{\text{knee5m_ab}}^2 =$	0.9592295	$S_{\text{knee5m_ab}} =$	$2.94795 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convknee5m_ab}} =$	$4,84908 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{knee15m_ab}} =$	$-9.14039 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K	$u_{a\text{knee15m_ab}} =$	$4.86161 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{\text{knee15m_ab}} =$	1.780577858 K/W	$u_{b\text{knee15m_ab}} =$	0.001565058 K/W
		$u_{a,b\text{knee15m_ab}} =$	$-6.95554 \cdot 10^{-15}$ K ² /W
$R_{\text{knee15m_ab}}^2 =$	0.970024943	$S_{\text{knee15m_ab}} =$	$3.94142 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convknee15m_ab}} =$	$6,48324 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

3. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{knee30m_ab}} =$	$-3.22432 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K	$u_{a\text{knee30m_ab}} =$	$5.42472 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{\text{knee30m_ab}} =$	2.288048166 K/W	$u_{b\text{knee30m_ab}} =$	0.001746334 K/W
		$u_{a,b\text{knee30m_ab}} =$	$-8.66014 \cdot 10^{-15}$ K ² /W
$R_{\text{knee30m_ab}}^2 =$	0.977230186	$S_{\text{knee30m_ab}} =$	$4.39794 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convknee30m_ab}} =$	$7,23418 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

4. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	$1.97003520 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K	$u_{a\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	$5.25941303 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
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$b_{\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	0.00104006 K/J	$u_{b\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	$1.44127887 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K/J
		$u_{a,b\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	$-5.89883549 \cdot 10^{-18}$ K ² /J
$R_{\text{knee_energy_ab}}^2 =$	0,81272095	$S_{\text{knee_energy_ab}} =$	$1.14423361 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convknee_energy_ab}} =$	$1,88215 \cdot 10^{-9}$ K

3.4 Shoulder

3.4.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{should5m_b}} =$	2.28773545 K/W	$u_{b\text{should5m_b}} =$	0.00040099 K/W
$R_{\text{should5m_b}}^2 =$	0.988382321011267	$S_{\text{should5m_b}} =$	$3.67294 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convshould5m_b}} =$	$6,04163 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{should15m_b}} =$	3.56581087 K/W	$u_{b\text{should15m_b}} =$	0.0005406969 K/W
$R_{\text{should15m_b}}^2 =$	0.99128182	$S_{\text{should15m_b}} =$	$4.95262 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convshould15m_b}} =$	$8,14656 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

3. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{should30m_b}} =$	4.45101618 K/W	$u_{b\text{should30m_b}} =$	0.00061052 K/W
$R_{\text{should30m_b}}^2 =$	0.99280986	$S_{\text{should30m_b}} =$	$5.592238 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convshould30m_b}} =$	$9,19867 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K

4. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n - number of points)
($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{\text{should_energy_b}} =$	0.00287617 K/J	$u_{b\text{should_energy_b}} =$	$2.35930492 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K/J
$R_{\text{should_energy_b}}^2 =$	0.54590741	$S_{\text{should_energy_b}} =$	$4.39708632 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{convshould_energy_b}} =$	$7,32772 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

Remark: Please note that the correlation coefficient indicates a weak linear relationship, compared to the dependence of temperature increase on the deposited power after 5, 15, and 30 minutes. Please compare with the correlation coefficient for $Y = \beta X$.

3.4.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 5 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{should}5m_ab} =$	$-7.38255777 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{a}should5m_ab} =$	$4.92146463 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{should}5m_ab} =$	2.44132357 K/W	$u_{\text{b}should5m_ab} =$	0.00107459 K/W
		$u_{\text{a,b}should5m_ab} =$	$-5.03894355 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{should}5m_ab}^2 =$	0.99231007	$S_{\text{should}5m_ab} =$	$2.98831680 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{conv}should5m_ab} =$	$4,91548 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$

2. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 15 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{should}15m_ab} =$	$-1.15296535 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{a}should15m_ab} =$	$6.02977586 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{should}15m_ab} =$	3.80567595 K/W	$u_{\text{b}should15m_ab} =$	0.00131658 K/W
		$u_{\text{a,b}should15m_ab} =$	$-7.56402739 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{should}15m_ab}^2 =$	0.99523567	$S_{\text{should}15m_ab} =$	$3.66128416 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{conv}should15m_ab} =$	$6,02245 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$

3. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 4 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{should}30m_ab} =$	$-1.36279491 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{a}should30m_ab} =$	$6.53230859 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{should}30m_ab} =$	4.73453459 K/W	$u_{\text{b}should30m_ab} =$	0.00142631 K/W
		$u_{\text{a,b}should30m_ab} =$	$-8,87736632 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ K}^2/\text{W}$
$R_{\text{should}30m_ab}^2 =$	0.99638305	$S_{\text{should}30m_ab} =$	$3,96642239 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{conv}should30m_ab} =$	$6,52437 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ K}$

4. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the energy (in J) (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 12 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{\text{should_energy_ab}} =$	$6.83287867 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$	$u_{\text{a}should_energy_ab} =$	$1.46611822 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ K}$
$b_{\text{should_energy_ab}} =$	0.00184608 K/J	$u_{\text{b}should_energy_ab} =$	$2.72507650 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K/J}$
		$u_{\text{a,b}should_energy_ab} =$	$-3,24048231 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ K}^2/\text{J}$
$R_{\text{should_energy_ab}}^2 =$	$0,79272417$	$S_{\text{should_energy_ab}} =$	$2.97078161 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,\text{conv}should_energy_ab} =$	$4,88664 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ K}$

3.5 All implants together

As a sample, evaluation for all data coming from all four implants at 30 minutes exposure were evaluated and the overall parameters were calculated.

3.5.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 16 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{all30m_b} =$	2,40313060 K/W	$u_{ball30m_b} =$	0,00067089 K/W
$R_{all30m_b^2} =$	0,97086364	$S_{all30m_b} =$	$5,69767662 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convall30m_b} =$	$9,37211 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power divided by the implant surface, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 16 \cdot 10^4$)

$b_{all30m_bS} =$	0,05714077 K/W·m ²	$u_{ball30m_bS} =$	0,00001001 K/W·m ²
$R_{all30m_bS^2} =$	0,98843460	$S_{all30m_bS} =$	$3,58971942 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convall30m_bS} =$	$5,90473 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

3.5.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

1. Linear regression $Y = \alpha + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 16 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{all30m_ab} =$	$4,45452985 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K	$u_{aall30m_ab} =$	$1,90138367 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{all30m_ab} =$	2,25120807 K/W	$u_{ball30m_ab} =$	0,00089554 K/W
		$u_{a,ball30m_ab} =$	$-1,23299078 \cdot 10^{-15}$ K ² /W
$R_{all30m_ab^2} =$	0,99231007	$S_{all30m_ab} =$	$2,98831680 \cdot 10^{-11}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,40\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convall30m_ab} =$	$8,62823 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

2. Linear regression $Y = a + \beta X$ for temperature increase depending on the deposited power divided by the implant surface, exposure of 30 minutes (n - number of points)

($1 - \alpha = 0,95, p = 0,9, n = 16 \cdot 10^4$)

$a_{all30m_abS} =$	$6,83287867 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K	$u_{aall30m_abS} =$	$1,35831111 \cdot 10^{-12}$ K
$b_{all30m_abS} =$	0,05640815 K/W	$u_{ball30m_abS} =$	$1,51425508 \cdot 10^{-5}$ K/W
		$u_{a,ball30m_abS} =$	$-1,55256325 \cdot 10^{-18}$ K ² /W
$R_{all30m_abS^2} =$	0,98860143	$S_{all30m_abS} =$	$3,56375607 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K
	$k_{2,0,975,0,9,120\ 000} = 1,6449$	$U_{y,convall30m_abS} =$	$5,86202 \cdot 10^{-10}$ K

4 SUMMARY OF THE TASK

4.1 Summarizing the results

The following tables compare the results of the two approaches:

- with a linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$
- with a linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

The main idea is comparing the declination of the regression line, i.e. the parameter b , regardless the shift of the line (represented by a parameter a) is considered. To do so, the deposited power in W was transferred to energy in J . Four cases were compared - three related to the time (5, 15, and 30 minutes), and one for the whole set of 120000 points (for any combination of the angles θ and φ it is one data point).

For the deposited power

Table 4.1 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

	Parameter	5 minutes	15 minutes	30 minutes
Ankle Plate	$b_{ankpla_b} / K/W$	1,4712125	2,115517798	2,552769599
Hip	$b_{hip_b} / K/W$	1,133156432	1,897958636	2,49762561
Knee	$b_{knee_b} / K/W$	1,145453	1,777887961	2,278559419
Shoulder	$b_{should_b} / K/W$	2,28773545	3,56581087	4,45101618

Table 4.2 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

	Parameter	5 minutes	15 minutes	30 minutes
Ankle Plate	a_{ankpla_ab} / K	$2.29836 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$3.111633 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$3.58566 \cdot 10^{-11}$
	$b_{ankpla_ab} / K/W$	1.230235528	1.788778401	2.17682236
Hip	a_{hip_ab} / K	$1.20576 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.13769 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.3879 \cdot 10^{-9}$
	$b_{hip_ab} / K/W$	1.09149561	1.504872446	2.018085947
Knee	a_{knee_ab} / K	$3.3659 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$-9.14039 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$-3.22432 \cdot 10^{-11}$
	$b_{knee_ab} / K/W$	1.135547694	1.780577858	2.288048166
Shoulder	a_{should_ab} / K	$-7.38255777 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$-1.15296535 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$-1.36279491 \cdot 10^{-10}$
	$b_{should_ab} / K/W$	2.44132357	3.80567595	4.73453459

For energy

Table 4.3 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

	Parameter	Value
Ankle Plate	$b_{ankpla_energy_b} / K/J$	0.00167640
Hip	$b_{hip_energy_b} / K/J$	0.001580637
Knee	$b_{knee_energy_b} / K/J$	0.00146018
Shoulder	$b_{should_energy_b} / K/J$	0.00287617

Table 4.4 For the linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

	Parameter	Value
Ankle Plate	$a_{ankpla_energy_ab} / K$	$5.41049901 \cdot 10^{-11}$
	$b_{ankpla_energy_ab} / K/J$	0.00126533
Hip	$a_{hip_energy_ab} / K$	$2.59697 \cdot 10^{-9}$

	$b_{\text{hip_energy_ab}} / \text{K/J}$	0.000930428
Knee	$a_{\text{knee_energy_ab}} / \text{K}$	$1.97003520 \cdot 10^{-9}$
	$b_{\text{knee_energy_ab}} / \text{K/J}$	0.00104006
Shoulder	$a_{\text{should_energy_ab}} / \text{K}$	$6.83287867 \cdot 10^{-10}$
	$b_{\text{should_energy_ab}} / \text{K/J}$	0.00184608

Example

As an example, the following table compares results for one case of exposure time and the same regression model. The last line represents the results for deposited energy divided by the surface.

Table 4.5 Comparison of parameters for 30 minutes exposure time and a model $Y = \beta X$

Implant	Model	$\Delta T \times 10^{-8} / \text{K}$	$U(\Delta T) \times 10^{-8} / \text{K}$	b	Deposited power $\times 10^{-9}$
Ankle plate	$\Delta T = b P$	0,003 - 0,06	0,006	2,55 K/W	0,01 - 0,09 W
Hip	$\Delta T = b P$	0,5 - 1	0,138	2,50 K/W	2 - 4 W
Knee	$\Delta T = b P$	0,06 - 1,1	0,072	2,28 K/W	0,5 - 5 W
Shoulder	$\Delta T = b P$	0,018 - 0,35	0,009	4,45 K/W	0 - 1 W
All 4 implants	$\Delta T = b P$	0,05- 1,1	0,094	2,40 K/W	$(0,5 - 5) \times 10^{-9} \text{ W}$
All 4 implants	$\Delta T = b \frac{P}{S}$	0,1- 1,1	0,0013	$0,057 \text{ K} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{W}}$	$(1,1 - 19) \times 10^{-8} \text{ W/m}^2$

It is worth noting from a physical point of view, one can observe a natural process of heating and heat transfer to the environment - the non-linear section of the graph indicates the heating of the implant itself from the moment the gradient coil is turned on, and the linear section demonstrates the transfer of heat from the implant to the surrounding tissues.

With increasing time, the direction of the magnetic field for maximum temperature rise approaches the direction of maximum energy storage in the implant. At the time of 30 minutes, they are already close.

4.2 What we learned so far? Questions and answers

Following is a short summary of facts, what we learned so far by processing the obtained data, and what is still needed to do.

What we obtained in general?

The linear relationship between the deposited power (energy, power divided by surface) and the temperature rise.

Which form gets this relationship?

This relationship we can approximate by linear regression in the form $Y = b X$ (of a line crossing through the zero point) or $Y = a + b X$ (a line shifted from the zero point)

With which restrictions?

For each implant, we took all information on power and the respective temperature increase as data points, regardless of the combination of angles and also the time of exposure. In other words, we did not investigate the way data were obtained, and purely statistical methods were applied

What is the usefulness of obtained relationship?

We can select the maximum temperature increase and we can derive the deposited power related to that temperature increase

What we cannot say from the obtained relationship?

We cannot say

- the way the deposited power was brought to the implant. In other words, we know the relationship

between the temperature increase and the magnitude of the incoming power, but we do not know the time of exposure and parameters of the magnetic field which generated the incoming power

- b) the influence of angles
- c) the influence of implant geometry with one exception, when we divided the incoming power by the surface of individual implants
- d) the maximum temperature at any given particular point of the implant. In other words, we know the general temperature rise in dependence on the acting power, either at one particular time or in a time interval, but not the temperature at any point of the implant
- e) the influence of time of exposure

What is needed in future investigations?

For further use of the model and its better complexity, the following information needs to be obtained and implemented:

- a) A model relationship between the measured MRI machine input parameters and the generated power, acting on the implant
- b) Influence of implant geometry on thermal distribution
- c) Limits for permissible temperature increase, time limits, and other limitations for implant exposure (what is the longest exposure of the implant)
- d) Other

5 GRAPHICAL RESULTS

5.1 Ankle plate

5.1.1 Ankle plate - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

5.1.2 Ankle plate - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

5.2 Hip

5.2.1 Hip - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

5.2.2 Hip - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

5.3 Knee

5.3.1 Knee - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

5.3.2 Knee - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

5.4 Shoulder

5.4.1 Shoulder - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

Figures for individual times are missing

5.4.2 Shoulder - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

5.5 All four implants together

5.5.1 All four implants together - linear regression in the form of $Y = \beta X$

5.5.2 All four implants together - linear regression in the form of $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

Task B: Performing a statistical analysis of the agreement between the experimental and numerical results.

1. DEFINITION OF THE TASK

The STASIS project proposal reads

Results from A3.1.6 and A3.2.2 were collected by INRIM. These correspond to temperature increase experiments together with the relevant results obtained from numerical simulations. Both experimental and numerical data are associated with an uncertainty value.

The task is to perform a **statistical analysis** in order to establish how much experimental results **match** with the numerical results also accounting for the relevant uncertainties.

In other words, following data are available (see Fig. B1)

- Temperature rise in K of a particular implant, simulation point, obtained by simulation in discrete samples of the exposition time (green line, uncertainty limits are also illustrated),
- The corresponding temperature rise in K of the same implant, the same measurement point and an overall experimental setup, obtained by experiment in discrete samples of the exposition time (orange line, uncertainty limits are also illustrated).

Figure B1. Graphical representation of the task
(Shown are data for Hip(RE), column 1 (measurement point 1))

The following implants were considered for the analysis: femur, hip, knee, shoulder, tibia. A total of 21 .mat files were received for analysis. Each .mat file refers to a specific experiment (experimental data + relevant simulation data). The filename reports the implant involved in the experiment, the type of experiment, the implant position (when relevant) and the used MR sequence. Each single Matlab file contains 6 arrays:

1. Experimental data:

time_resampled(:,1)

Column vector with time samples

ch_resampled(:,1:nc)

Column vector with temperature samples; Each column refers to a temperature channel (measurement point)

<code>error_tot_meas(:,1:nc)</code>	Column vector with expanded uncertainties (2-sigma level) of each temperature sample; Each column refers to a temperature channel (<u>measurement</u> point)
2. Simulated data:	
<code>time_model(:,1)</code>	Column vector with time samples
<code>ch_model(:,1:nc)</code>	Column vector with temperature samples; Each column refers to a temperature channel (simulation point)
<code>error_tot_model(:,1:nc)</code>	Column vector with expanded uncertainties (2-sigma level) of each temperature sample; Each column refers to a temperature channel (<u>simulation</u> point)

One needs to realize that the number of time samples is different for measured and simulated data.

2. SOLUTION

To mathematically express how the simulated data corresponded to the measured data, a suitable approach had to be chosen first. Both simulated and measured data were available, which were obtained at discrete time points during the total exposure time. In addition, the measurement uncertainty was assigned to the individual simulated and measured data.

A simple plot of the simulated and measured data (including the uncertainty) as a function of time only provided a visual representation of how the simulated and measured data gradually differed from each other (see Fig. B2). Due to the consideration of measurement uncertainty, even this simple representation showed that it was not possible to answer the question of how the simulated data corresponded to the measured data unambiguously.

A different approach was therefore chosen (see Fig. B3). A set of data points (x_i, y_i) was created, where x_i was the simulated value and y_i was the measured value. Of course, the simulated and measured values correspond to the same time point, i.e. they were obtained at the same time. This is how the dependence of simulated or measured values on time was changed to the dependence between simulated and measured values. This approach made it possible to use the methodology used in the calibration of measuring instruments. A straight line can be then fitted through the individual data points (x_i, y_i) , $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, the parameters of which also reflected the associated measurement uncertainty. Ideally, with complete agreement between simulated and measured data, the straight line should pass through zero and the slope of the straight line should be equal to one. Deviations from this ideal dependence are reflected in the values of the slope of the straight line and its displacement relative to zero.

This approach has the disadvantage that it does not take into account the physical limitations resulting from the theoretically obtained parameters of the straight line.

Figure B2. Visualization of simulated (model) data and measured (experimental) data vs. heating time for a single instance Hip(RE)

2.1 Use of the straight-line function

For determining the relationship among the simulated and measured data in the whole range of exposure times, a document ISO/TS 28037:2010 *Determination and use of straight-line calibration functions* was employed.

The named document is concerned with linear, that is, straight-line functions that describe the relationship between two variables X and Y , namely, function of the form $Y = A + BX$. In our case, variable X represents simulated data, while variable Y represents measured data (see Figure B3).

Figure B3. Graphical representation of the simulated and measured data

Values of the parameters A and B are determined based on measured data points (x_i, y_i) , $i = 1, \dots, m$. In our case, x_i represent simulated data, while y_i represent the measured data. Of course, each data point (x_i, y_i) from the set contains simulated and measured data obtained at the same time. Therefore, for determining the straight-line function between the simulated and measured data, we took a number of data points (x_i, y_i) , obtained within the given exposure time.

It is assumed that all x_i and y_i data are accompanied by the associated uncertainties $u(x_i)$ and $u(y_i)$ respectively. No assumption is made that the errors relating to the y_i are homoscedastic (having equal variance), and similarly for the x_i when the errors are not negligible.

Estimates a, b of the parameters A and B are determined using least squares methods. Moreover, the associated uncertainties $u(a)$ and $u(b)$ to parameters a, b are determined, as well as covariance $u(a, b)$ between the parameters a, b .

ISO/TS 28037:2010 also describes the use of the straight-line function parameter estimates and their associated uncertainties and covariance to predict a value of X and its associated standard uncertainty, respectively forward evaluate the value of Y and its associated standard uncertainty.

2.2 Calculation of the straight-line function parameters

The procedure for calculating the parameters A, B is described in the part 7 *Model for uncertainties associated with the x_i and the y_i* of the document ISO/TS 28037:2010. This part describes in detail the determination of estimates a, b , and determination of the associated uncertainties and a covariance between the parameters.

The described procedure assumes that the following information is provided for $i = 1, \dots, m$:

- simulated data x_i and measurement data y_i , grouped in the set of data points (x_i, y_i) ,
- standard uncertainty $u(x_i)$ associated with x_i , and
- standard uncertainty $u(y_i)$ associated with y_i .

All covariances associated with the data are regarded as negligible.

The iterative scheme for parameters estimation is employed. In the first step, a standard least squares method is used for determining the initial estimates a_0, b_0 of the searched parameters. Then the increments δa and δb are repeatedly determined and sequentially added to the previous estimates of parameters a, b . The whole process finishes by evaluating the specific chi-squared test. Then the corresponding uncertainties and covariance are calculated (see Fig. B4).

Figure B4. The example of the calculated approximation line (HIP(RE), column 1)

2.3 Use of the determined straight-line function parameters

The straight-line function with known parameters a , b , the associated uncertainties $u(a)$, $u(b)$ and a covariance $u(a,b)$ provides us with a mathematical expression allowing to determine the dependence among simulated and measured data. Once the function and associated data are known, two possible ways of employing the determined function can be considered:

- prediction - measured value y of Y and associated standard uncertainty $u(y)$ is known. The task is to determine the corresponding simulated value x of X , and an associated uncertainty $u(x)$, or
- forward evaluation - simulated value x of X and associated standard uncertainty $u(x)$ is known. The task is to determine the corresponding measured value y of Y , and an associated uncertainty $u(y)$.

As written earlier, in both cases it is assumed that straight-line parameters estimates a and b , and standard uncertainties $u(a)$ and $u(b)$ and a covariance $cov(a, b)$ associated with a and b are known.

Prediction

Consider that measured value y has been obtained independently of the measurement data used to establish the straight-line function. The estimate x of simulated parameter X is

$$x = \frac{y - a}{b}$$

The standard uncertainty $u(x)$, associated with x , is calculated according to the Law of propagation of uncertainties as

$$u^2(x) = c^2(a)u^2(a) + c^2(b)u^2(b) + c^2(y)u^2(y) + 2c(a)c(b)cov(a, b)$$

where $c(a)$, $c(b)$, $c(y)$ are sensitivity coefficients

$$c(a) = -\frac{1}{b}$$

$$c(b) = -\frac{y - a}{b^2}$$

$$c(y) = \frac{1}{b}$$

Forward evaluation

The estimate y of Y corresponding to x is

$$y = a + bx$$

The standard uncertainty $u(y)$ associated with y is given by

$$u^2(y) = c^2(a)u^2(a) + c^2(b)u^2(b) + c^2(x)u^2(x) + 2c(a)c(b)\text{cov}(a, b)$$

where $c(a)$, $c(b)$, $c(y)$ are sensitivity coefficients

$$c(a) = 1, c(b) = x, c(x) = b$$

2.4 Summary to the selected approach

This approach allows us to either evaluate the measurement according to the simulated data, or to predict the simulated value based on the measurements. In any case, the corresponding uncertainty can be calculated, which brings an additional quality to the obtained dependence among the simulated and measured data. The straight-line function allows to mathematically evaluate the matching between the simulated and measured data. This further enables more detailed analysis of individual implants, simulation models and sample measurements, which yields in a better understanding of implant heating under different occasions.

3 CALCULATIONS

In the previous sections, we defined

- a) the principal question to be answered: how much the experimental results match with the numerical results accounting for the relevant uncertainties.
- b) the input data received – totally 21 *.mat files with simulated and experimental data,
- c) the selected approach for solving the principal question – establishing a straight-line function, that defines the relation among simulated and experimental data.

Now let us define the types of calculations that should be carried out.

As written earlier, a lot of simulated and measured data is available, depending on the type of experiment as well as the type of the implant to be addressed. Therefore, many combinations of input data (simulated vs. experimental) can be employed, for which the straight-line function can be determined.

When coordinating the research activities among INRIM, ČMI and STU, the following four groups of calculations were defined:

1. All data together, all files, times, columns
Take all the data received (all *.mat files, all instances, all times, all implants), put them together, and make a single line over them. It includes Femur, Hip, Knee, Shoulder, and Tibia implants, all times, and all columns. The output desired are parameters for a single line, covering all implants and all instances
2. For one instance (one time) mix all data from all implants.
Take all the data from all implants (Femur, Hip, Knee, Shoulder, and Tibia) and all columns, but only for a particular time (for a single particular row). Totally 3 versions shall be evaluated: 300 s, 600 s, 900 s. The output is parameters for the three lines (time 300 s, 600 s, 900 s)
3. Take one implant, mix all data related to the implant together
Take all the data from all files and columns, for all times, but separately for a single implant. The output is parameters for four lines (femur, knee, tibia, shoulder)
4. Individual evaluations on individual separate data sets
Take only separate data for a particular implant and particular instance and particular column. The output is parameters for a specific line related to a given data set.

The following table B.1 summarizes the results for the obtained data set NEW_DATA_INRIM_DATA_VS2. The evaluation of the obtained results, i.e. parameters of the straight-line function, is performed by INRIM, and reported in their deliverables.

Table B.1 Results of the straight-line function for the data set obtained

			<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>u(a)</i>	<i>u(b)</i>	Covariance <i>u(a,b)</i>	<i>r</i>
Task 1		All data	-0.004907905185139	0.924327743761982	0.002693956867838	0.025767880339540	-3.054564128133216e-05	16.356225461292260
Task 2	Femur	200 s	-0.004730217587454	0.764718356179748	0.008910662518204	0.054692237926329	-3.943972340959600e-04	12.628808844127024
		400 s	0.005484039284024	0.794856667329768	0.016632775139442	0.057877198517401	-7.891698747274929e-04	6.153752039199373
		600 s	0.008816646973441	0.846492742818379	0.023261674414261	0.060293704812444	-0.001143871188974	2.934548380175607
		900 s	0.019996056335162	0.902026680656433	0.032540845293747	0.063432356664473	-0.001668952276106	1.518828987277543
	Hip	200 s	0.032811974462212	0.675617192505557	0.007072946246634	0.026867613797268	-1.478000675677771e-04	71.048007289867640
		400 s	0.084510037995691	0.706981615857333	0.012459134533751	0.029064187803765	-2.818537343583272e-04	43.416643501154084
		600 s	0.111144500822584	0.734546879023881	0.037975359708094	0.039849506044676	-0.001234784942520	9.852844269361958
		900 s	0.142266773037649	0.770801042214080	0.051051413169259	0.042812645885891	-0.001806335746488	9.384097184437433
	Knee	200 s	-0.032700997000726	1.363775029442935	0.014226073886945	0.100974986207993	-0.001258899417226	56.425459240637615
		400 s	-0.086568159309177	1.599471865771367	0.031151828999689	0.132949206001708	-0.003777865631926	47.715613021277810
		600 s	-0.016167458845686	0.948402139155403	0.068575618419529	0.176310022995135	-0.010795593998282	1.398042607547288
		900 s	-0.008410344367889	0.975509217870057	0.101381672501821	0.202210521678653	-0.018725419437812	0.937575813899910
	Shoulder	200 s	0.092348790812444	0.605476218531904	0.021853895529061	0.044989454137160	-8.810759574447535e-04	63.192080641849046
		400 s	0.135806389583340	0.664324351155069	0.035654762816244	0.049739998863051	-0.001602071216622	38.862364904973470
		600 s	-6.942268151502020	6.662260323516325	5.259269630098430	4.422615337265153	-23.252142515793548	6.609665129465449
		900 s	-8.448816378108440	6.852350502801359	7.111394417175920	5.045863739893506	-35.872930040495824	5.012914868532930
	Tibial	200 s	0.007981113298991	0.747216771432548	0.018756384837045	0.032845168480118	-5.036758959273508e-04	15.039333715460039
		400 s	-0.012373094230415	0.851839266200256	0.028255461147689	0.036981250849329	-8.595562018906676e-04	9.990926533472772
		600 s	-0.043726806293060	0.925261632810579	0.035578652206837	0.039586481317741	-0.001160989179935	4.878173260086101
		900 s	-0.058557238649261	0.972882215768814	0.043985242614225	0.041628823001058	-0.001513425989819	3.502485857130775
All implants	200 s	0.019404360162885	0.747732444719381	0.004004268972022	0.014975736364059	-4.409892159967782e-05	3.298069621031615e+02	
	400 s	0.047282489207037	0.797156939505872	0.007333200626946	0.016940397573535	-9.519947247492448e-05	2.630251338560409e+02	

		600 s	0.012029267473151	0.843408051415499	0.014173075703090	0.020017327043491	-2.192219973245130e-04	57.266271836093990
		900 s	0.023309698882737	0.879474979322333	0.019556198278792	0.021759148159872	-3.371221376833681e-04	51.079917132521660
Task 3	Femur	All data	-0.006232712451246	0.974316799768952	0.002636770831267	0.015137320761821	-1.785595462315558e-05	22.031284019898187
	Hip	All data	-0.010127130291883	0.981961439309857	0.003091733874135	0.037031500592081	-8.783850728521455e-05	8.663269118337070
	Knee	All data	-0.025655599242253	0.635730970788776	0.004724296366429	0.025062916742844	-8.769111124247974e-05	40.491842193596625
	Shoulder	All data	-0.007870851702194	0.602963188245692	0.002278225200328	0.019661337835525	-2.033082567756539e-05	28.873495789406000
	Tibial	All data	-0.029140236234364	0.846196607619542	0.003503254322056	0.013505486922342	-3.597166595319500e-05	53.408775848999454
Task 4	Femur	(RE) Column 1	-0.006232718194965	0.974316840921663	0.002636770204518	0.015137311789100	-1.785593812292627e-05	22.031284019276782
		(RE) Column 2	-0.008476106084576	1.094590662635126	0.002057347855561	0.027751097606440	-4.055233576945168e-05	7.523012472448466
		(RE) Column 3	-0.005898772150929	0.934139807147304	0.001142507077300	0.022498232107492	-1.583725406549432e-05	16.890858701944012
		(WO) Column 1	-0.014480766272367	0.819962538854963	0.003120426729800	0.007300288348353	-6.840082202684264e-06	2.157251420955415e+02
		(WO) Column 2	-0.025935624908013	0.882618375809857	0.001865718639896	0.009087580699284	-1.200322437929293e-05	1.277057052346939e+02
		(WO) Column 3	-0.017089974693584	0.801482938072242	0.001096810204045	0.010254121944293	-7.193855497312013e-06	1.493173819253223e+02
	Hip	(RE) Column 1	-0.016743859722609	1.105160605337667	0.002636829337239	0.019618394120527	-3.627700103513687e-05	26.234347983448260
		(RE) Column 2	-0.057813095789869	0.771213156107088	0.003902334649557	0.009282837603295	-2.421292971189638e-05	2.036805548965392e+02
		(RE) Column 3	-0.023709808684009	0.707954247349384	0.001870730219673	0.007596874347081	-7.300274677495872e-06	1.333386488648540e+02
		(WO) Column 1	-0.018073454641214	1.236555055376612	0.001919757451050	0.017692451049411	-2.034602034536907e-05	74.326988493140850
		(WO) Column 2	-0.052194553032637	0.835559397697266	0.004194794132810	0.005473999054752	-1.473461300988362e-05	1.616714292884419e+02
		(WO) Column 3	-0.033560775212565	0.838425625804233	0.002162951775858	0.005504634667619	-6.080451653533217e-06	2.057898045903108e+02
	Knee	(RE) Column 1	-0.043192999226446	0.825570125801035	0.004467118540836	0.016276953256501	-4.994158398155970e-05	1.135774387648894e+02
		(RE) Column 2	-0.034538552005863	1.017801716943328	0.005382778567051	0.018862084421613	-6.719419224789433e-05	57.858114601268085
		(RE) Column 3	-0.004030894372869	0.931333152977411	0.001772915161297	0.022608818513522	-2.505432986681995e-05	15.584181236160006
	Shoulder	(RE) Column 1	-0.011368711127394	0.700416319819935	0.002232891632581	0.012204125617612	-1.017234028905895e-05	64.443861744462030
		(RE) Column 2	-0.014974527951590	0.869540334505379	0.003651757261737	0.013406528752676	-1.909794711220192e-05	47.972676598516190
		(RE) Column 3	-0.007459415085771	0.930055126903404	0.002330648427774	0.012099748784110	-9.194749181638742e-06	29.768809127857107
(WO) Column 1		-0.030981907741031	0.615641030688305	0.002055573339668	0.005539338887334	-6.254061891484881e-06	3.316615129318416e+02	

	(WO) Column 2	-0.056188927881634	0.791370820236438	0.003103801211024	0.006036364482795	-1.185521993983736e-05	4.079458835598822e+02
	(WO) Column 3	-0.015783600211746	0.962898933063130	0.001961545555037	0.006200481008795	-5.628324898417632e-06	1.049761210610379e+02
Tibial	(RE) Column 1	-0.029140148368575	0.846196270801262	0.003503268711441	0.013505577273523	-3.597206005349667e-05	53.408775893887970
	(RE) Column 2	-0.036696178580039	0.828405139241780	0.003857732286419	0.014700399118551	-4.213683677797982e-05	92.797142743558070
	(RE) Column 3	-0.017247590112678	0.909471049544661	0.002918067420570	0.014883774207750	-3.251342842190504e-05	22.514565823455534
	(WO) Column 1	-0.084158194884998	0.864489155796940	0.004431159689568	0.005524489017350	-1.703726454715574e-05	6.613607628106338e+02
	(WO) Column 2	-0.079704878088096	0.839609160589047	0.004164139515233	0.005569931423752	-1.504637522552644e-05	6.559714187593834e+02
	(WO) Column 3	-0.044828414879061	0.965986355332829	0.003549813677295	0.006034187194786	-1.347092352156828e-05	2.381353580279230e+02

CONCLUSION

In summary, an open-source reference hardware consisting of an 8-channel 3T pTx body coil, performant parallel transmission RF exposure hardware and operating software have been developed, which is suitable, amongst others, for offline implant testing by manufacturers or test houses.

More detailed information on the reference hardware and software can be found in the public repositories, and its application is further detailed in deliverable D1 of the STASIS project.

The aims of the STASIS project deliverable have been successfully achieved, fulfilling Objective 2 of the project.